

BC-SIM-TR-044

SIMBIO-SYS ICO#05

Interchannel Test Report

Michele Zusi¹, Emanuele Simioni², Vincenzo Della Corte¹, Andrea Cichetti¹,
Romolo Politi¹,
Gabriele Cremonese², Fabrizio Capaccioni¹, Alain Doressundiram³,
Pasquale Palumbo¹, Cristina Re², Mathieu Vincendon⁴

¹INAF-IAPS, Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Rome, Italy

²INAF-OAPd, Vicolo Osservatorio 5, 35122, Padua, Italy

³LESIA (Observatoire de Paris - PSL, Laboratoire d'Études Spatiales et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique), 92195 Meudon Cedex, France

⁴CNRS (Institut d'Astrophysique Spatiale), Université Paris Sud, 91405, Orsay, France

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	1 of 20		

Index

Approval	2
Document change record	2
1. Introduction	3
1.1. Scope	3
1.2. Reference documents	3
1.3. Acronyms	4
1.4. Document format and repository	5
1.5. Document organization	5
2. SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment description	6
2.1. SIMBIO-SYS CF sensors	6
2.2. SIMBIO-SYS thermal sensors	8
3. SIMBIO-SYS Interchannel Test	9
3.1. SIMBIO-SYS Interference Test	9
3.1.1. Test description	9
3.1.2. Commanding	11
3.1.3. HK Interpretation	13
3.1.4. Data Analysis	16
4. Conclusions	20

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	2 of 20		

Approvation

Edited by:	Michele Zusi
	Emanuele Simioni
	Vincenzo Della Corte
	Andrea Cicchetti
Approved by:	Fabrizio Capaccioni
	Cristina Re
	Pasquale Palumbo
	Gabriele Cremonese

Document change record

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description
1	0	04/10/2024	All	First issue

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	3 of 20		

1.Introduction

1.1. Scope

This document contains the results and the discussion on the Interchannel Tests performed during the Instrument check Out 05 (ICO#05) for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS) described in [RD.1].

1.2. Reference documents

- [RD.1]** BC-SIM-PL-008_-_SIMBIO-SYS_Checkout_05_Test_Summary_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.5281/zenodo.11208000](https://zenodo.org/record/11208000)
- [RD.2]** BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/36](https://www.inaf.it/2023/10/20371/INAF/TechRep/36)
- [RD.3]** BC-ALS-TN-00099 MPO PFM Monitoring Thermistors Location
- [RD.4]** BC-SIM-TR-041_-_STC_ICO#05_report,
[10.5281/zenodo.12515578](https://zenodo.org/record/12515578)
- [RD.5]** BC-SIM-TR-042_-_HRIC_ICO#05_report
- [RD.6]** BC-SIM-TR-043_-_VIHI_ICO#05_report
- [RD.7]** BC-SIM-TR-019_-_STC_ICO#02_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/138](https://www.inaf.it/2023/10/20371/INAF/TechRep/138)
- [RD.8]** BC-SIM-TR-018_-_HRIC_ICO#02_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/134](https://www.inaf.it/2023/10/20371/INAF/TechRep/134)
- [RD.9]** BC-SIM-TN-013 STC Inflight Dark Calibration
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/210](https://www.inaf.it/2023/10/20371/INAF/TechRep/210)
- [RD.10]** BC-SIM-TR-007_-_STC_dNECP_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/71](https://www.inaf.it/2023/10/20371/INAF/TechRep/71)
- [RD.11]** BC-SIM-TR-028_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#03_Interchannel_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/197](https://www.inaf.it/2023/10/20371/INAF/TechRep/197)
- [RD.12]** BC-SIM-TR-034_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04_Interchannel_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.5281/zenodo.8366159](https://zenodo.org/record/8366159)

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	4 of 20		

[RD.13]BC-SIM-TR-038_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04b_Interchannel_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.5281/zenodo.10649965](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10649965)

[RD.14]BC-SIM-TN-004_-_SIMBIO-SYS_FOP_update_after_NECP,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/58](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/58)

[RD.15]BC-SIM-TR-040_-_EGSE_ICO5_Report,
[10.5281/zenodo.10068973](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10068973)

1.3. Acronyms

ASW	Application SoftWare
ACK	Acknowledgement
CF	Cold Finger
dNECP	delta Near Earth Commissioning Phase
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
ODS	Offset Dark Subtraction
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PE	Proximity Electronics
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSMM	Solid State Mass Memory
STC	STereo imaging Channel
S/C	Space-Craft
TC	TeleCommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler
VIHI	VIsible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	5 of 20		

1.4. Document format and repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.2] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.5. Document organization

This document is organized in sections whose topics are listed as follows:

- Section 2 – SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment description, with a brief description of the aboard units and sensors used to control the operative temperature of the instrument during the test
- Section 3 – Interchannel test results and discussion
- Section 4 – Some conclusions on the ICO#05 Interchannel activities are reported

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	6 of 20		

2.SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment description

The SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment is controlled by means of the Space-Craft (S/C) dedicated Cold Fingers (CFs) and several thermal sensors which are described in the following subsections.

2.1. SIMBIO-SYS CF sensors

In the following table the list of CF temperature sensors for the three channels is reported. To note that all sensors are fixed on the S/C CF.

Channel	Sensor name	ESA ID	THALES ID
HRIC	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-HRIC-CF	NRUD2079	THT-B6T133
STC	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STC-CF	NRUD2087	THT-B6T136
VIHI	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-VIHI-CF	NRUD2091	THT-B6T137

Table 1: CF sensors of the SIMBIO-SYS channels together with their reference to ESA and Theles Alenia nomenclature (see [RD.3] for details)

For more details on their positions see [RD.3].

During the execution of the ICO#05 tests its value was monitored with a 5-minute frequency; the obtained trend is reported in Figure 1.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	7 of 20		

Figure 1: SIMBIO-SYS Cold Finger temperature during the ICO#05 Interchannel test (18:00 21:00) test. Temperature is reported in °C.

Figure 1 shows that all **SIMBIO-SYS CFs** were at the temperature thresholds and maintained the instrument at the expected temperature for all the duration of the test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	8 of 20		

2.2. SIMBIO-SYS thermal sensors

For the monitoring of its thermal behaviour, the SIMBIO-SYS instrument is equipped by the following sensors:

- **STC**

PACKET ID: YSS40002		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS21040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS21041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS21042	Temperature PE	K
NSS21043	Temp FPA_Package	K
NSS21044	Temp OpticalBench	K

Table 2: Main STC temperature sensors.

See [RD.4] for more details on their definition and position.

- **HRIC**

PACKET ID: YSS40001		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS11040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS11041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS11042	Temperature PE	K
NSS11043	Temp TIRD Filter	K
NSS11044	Temp FPA package	K

Table 3: Main HRIC temperature sensors.

See [RD.5] for more details on their definition and position.

- **VIHI**

PACKET ID: YSS40003		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS31040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS31041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS31042	Temperature PE	K
NSS31062	Temp Spectrometer	K
NSS31063	Temp Calibration unit	K

Table 4: Main VIHI temperature sensors.

See [RD.6] for more details on their definition and position.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	9 of 20		

3.SIMBIO-SYS Interchannel Test

3.1. SIMBIO-SYS Interference Test

3.1.1. Test description

The aim of the test is **the monitoring of low frequency behaviour** (see [RD.7] for STC and [RD.8] for HRIC channel) and **the impact of simultaneous acquisitions of two channels on this effect**.

Previous analysis showed a carrier wave with an amplitude of 6 Digital Number (DN) and a period of 3 minutes on the mean signal of the STC and HRIC acquisitions.

The interference between the two channels has minimal impact on the DC (both comparable with the ReadOut Noise). In any case the effect is uniform on the FPA which means that the DC Offset Dark Subtraction (see [RD.9]) applied during images calibration will remove this bias without effect on the performances.

This phenomenon, measured for STC during the Orbit test (see [RD.10]) required additive tests during ICO3 (see [RD.11]) including the two imaging Channels and during ICO4 (see [RD.12]) and ICO4b (see [RD.13]) including even VIHI channel.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	10 of 20		

A summary of the LFB measurement for the STC case is reported in following table.

ICO	Test Name	Channels	Science TC RT [s]	LFB Period [min]	TPE [K]	H1 Period [min]	H2 Period [min]	CF Period [min]
#3	Interference	HRIC	2	2.62	286-288	6	On	8
#4	Functional	STC	2	2.37	278.9	On	Off	N/A
#4	Interference	HRIC	2	1.56	281.6	On	Off	N/A
#4	Interference	HRIC	1	1.7	283.7	On	Off	N/A
#4	Interference	HRIC	2	1.87	284.9	On	Off	N/A
#4	Interference	HRIC	1	1.9	285.6	On	Off	N/A
#4b	Interference	HRIC/VIHI	1	2.56	285.9	On	Off	7
#4b	Interference	HRIC/VIHI	1	2.18	288.2	On	Off	7
#5	Functional	STC	2	9	286	On	7	15
#5	LFB	STC	0.8, 7, 12.3	15?	288.4	On	7.6	15
#5	Interference	STC/VIHI	1.5	2.68	285.7-288.5	On	9	11.6
#5	Interference	STC/HRIC	1	2.6	287-289	On	10.3	10

Table 5: LFB analysis evolution during ICOs: the periods for the heaters power supplies and CF temperature are reported for comparison with the given channel mean signal oscillation period.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	11 of 20		

3.1.2. Commanding

The test has been performed through the execution of a PDORs named: "POR_BPSS00875_SIMBIOSYS_ALL_ICO#05_Interchannel_test" (see attachments of [RD.1]).

A detailed timeline of the test is shown in Table 6.

Execution time	Sequence description	Sequence name
18:00:00	SIMBIO-SYS STC PE Detector TEC On by OBCP	ASSF008A
18:15:01	SIMBIO-SYS VIHI Science Mode Variable IT	ASSF512A
18:15:31	SIMBIO-SYS STC Out Filters SURF X	ASSF320A
18:25:01	SIMBIO-SYS VIHI Science Mode Variable IT	ASSF512A
18:35:01	SIMBIO-SYS VIHI Science Mode Variable IT	ASSF512A
18:45:21	VIHI STOP	ASSF514A
18:45:51	STC STOP	ASSF368A
18:46:00	STC OFF OBCP	ASSF007A
18:50:00	SIMBIO-SYS HRIC PE Detector TEC on by OBCP	ASSF005A
19:05:01	SIMBIO-SYS VIHI Science Mode Variable IT	ASSF512A
19:05:31	HRIC Science Acq Short Integr ALL FREE	ASSF100A
19:15:01	SIMBIO-SYS VIHI Science Mode Variable IT	ASSF512A
19:25:01	SIMBIO-SYS VIHI Science Mode Variable IT	ASSF512A
19:35:21	VIHI STOP	ASSF514A
19:35:51	HRIC Stop	ASSF110A
19:36:00	VIHI OFF OBCP	ASSF010A
19:40:00	STC PE Detector TEC On by OBCP	ASSF008A
19:56:02	HRIC Science Acq Short Integr ALL FREE	ASSF100A
20:42:21	STC STOP	ASSF368A
20:42:22	HRIC Stop	ASSF110A
20:42:30	HRIC OFF by OBCP	ASSF004A
20:46:30	STC OFF by OBCP	ASSF007A
20:50:30	ME OFF by OBCP	ASSF002A

Table 6: Timeline of the ICO#05 interchannel test with the references to the commanded FOPs (see [RD.14] for more details).

The resulting executions TeleCommand (TC) database derived by means of the Electric Ground Segment Equipment (EGSE) telemetry-to-raw pipeline is reported in Table 7, Table 8 and Table 9 (see [RD.15] for details) highlighting the used Repetition Time (RT) for each channel.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	12 of 20		

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration	RT [s]	# acq
1	2021-06-21 19:05:31	00:30:20	1.5	1213
2	2021-06-21 19:56:03	00:46:23	1	2769

Table 7: Resulting database of the Interchannel Test for the HRIC channel.

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration	RT [s]	# acq
1	2021-06-21 18:15:31	00:30:20	1.5	1214
2	2021-06-21 19:56:01	00:46:23	1	2780

Table 8: Resulting database of the Interchannel Test for the STC channel.

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration	RT[s]	# acq
1	2021-06-21 18:15:01	00:10:00	1	600
2	2021-06-21 18:25:01	00:10:00	1	600
3	2021-06-21 18:35:01	00:10:20	1	620
4	2021-06-21 19:05:01	00:10:00	1	600
5	2021-06-21 19:15:01	00:10:00	1	600
6	2021-06-14 19:25:01	00:10:20	1	620

Table 9: Resulting database of the Interchannel Test for the VIHI channel.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	13 of 20		

3.1.3. HK Interpretation

Figure 2 and Figure 3 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the STC channel during the test.

All HK are reported science TEC switch on 2021-06-21T18:00:00 with HK sampling of 30s.

Figure 2: STC Temperatures evolution over the ICO#05 interchannel test.

Figure 3: STC TEC current evolution over the ICO#05 interchannel test.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show a **nominal trend for the FPA temperature and TEC current of STC channel** no Out-Of-Limit (OOL) in the current profile occurred (i.e., no peak).

Figure 4 and Figure 5 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the HRIC channel during the test while using the new uploaded parameters for the TEC "soft" activation.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	14 of 20		

All HK are reported science TEC switch on 2021-06-21T18:40:00 with HK sampling of 30s.

Figure 4: HRIC Temperatures evolution over the ICO#05 interchannel test.

Figure 5: HRIC Tec current evolution over the ICO#05 interchannel test.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show, **as per the HRIC channel, a nominal trend for the FPA temperature and TEC current.**

Figure 6 and Figure 7 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the VIHI channel during the test.

All HK are reported science first VIHI HK 2021-06-21T18:00:00 with HK sampling of 10s.

Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
Date	04/10/2024		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page	15 of 20		

Figure 6: VIHI Temperature evolution over the ICO#05 interchannel test.

Figure 7: VIHI TEC current evolution over the ICO#05 interchannel test

As per STC and HRIC channel, their behaviour is nominal.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	16 of 20		

3.1.4. Data Analysis

Figure 8 shows the mean DC values for all the SIMBIO-SYS channels during the Interchannel Test.

Considering that the Dark level for the different channel is extremely different we correct all the different signals by removing the mean value in order to see them along the x axis.

HRIC is depicted in yellow, STC in green and VIHI in blue,

Figure 8 can be divided in three different phases:

- In the first part (left side) the output of VIHI/STC parallel operations,
- in the second part (middle) the VIHI/HRIC results
- while in the third part (right side) the results of the HRIC/STC parallel operations.

Figure 8: Mean DC values for all the channels during all the Interchannel Test.

For the first phase Figure 9 highlights the test results in the case of **VIHI/STC parallel operations**: detailed analysis indicates that **the operativity of one channel does not affect the other**. In particular, STC fluctuation (i.e., LFB) does not change in amplitude and period throughout the test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	17 of 20		

Figure 9: VIHI/STC parallel operations results.

The VIHI/HRIC case (Figure 10) seems quite similar to the VIHI/STC one apart from an unexpected evolution in time (i.e., frequency reduction) of the HRIC LFB. Considering Table 9 commanding (i.e., no particular VIHI activations), it seems a transient HRIC behaviour as soon as the channel is powered on.

Figure 10: VIHI/RHIC parallel operations results.

Finally, the STC/HRIC case (Figure 11) is very similar to the VIHI/HRIC case with, again, the unexpected lowering of the HRIC LFB frequency.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	18 of 20		

Figure 11: STC/RHIC parallel operations results.

The HRIC unexpected LFB behaviour shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11 is summarized in Figure 12 where the variation of the LFB period (cycle duration between two consecutive maximums) throughout the Interchannel Test execution is shown. It is evident that, **for STC the LFB period remains more or less constant during both the parallel tests with VIHI and HRIC; for HRIC, the LFB period significantly increases in both tests.**

Figure 12: HRIC and STC LFB period variation during ICO#05 Interchannel test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	19 of 20		

As a major point, **HRIC data profile in Figure 12 supports the transient behaviour of HRIC LFB anticipated while discussing Figure 10 explaining some its unconfirmed dependence from the RT seen in previous ICOs.**

It should be noted, for greater accuracy, that in this test where the LFB behaves differently between the two channels, STC and HRIC, the channels are not used symmetrically (as described in 3.1.3): the STC sequences are executed after the channel is turned on and then off, whereas the HRIC channel remains on during the second and third phases.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-044		
	Date	04/10/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	20 of 20		

4. Conclusions

During the SIMBIO-SYS ICO#05 the SIMBIO-SYS team requested to repeat the Interchannel test performed during previous ICO#04b [RD.13] to better details the mutual interference occurring while the three channels work in parallel. In particular, the test foreseen to evaluate such effect in three combinations of parallel operations:

1. VIHI and STC
2. VIHI and HRIC
3. STC and HRIC

putting the **channels in constant configuration and synchronizing the Science TC execution of one channel with the repetition of the one (i.e., same TC) of the other channel.**

Obtained results:

- 1. indicates that no interference is present while two channels synchronously run in constant configuration**
- 2. shows a possible transient variation of LFB frequency for the HRIC channel immediately after its power-on**

In conclusion, the Interchannel Test executed during the SIMBIO-SYS ICO#05 demonstrate that synchronous operations between different channels does not have any effects of the expected performance. In addition, the possible dependence of LFB effect from the RT, partially observed in past data, seems to be a simple transient effect occurring just after the channel power-on.

Regarding the parallel operation effect on LFB observed during [RD.13] additional tests may be required.